

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Gamma coloring of Mycielskian graphs

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Abstract

Background: Given a graph G , the gamma coloring problem seeks for a proper coloring C of G with the property that there exists a dominating set of G in which all the vertices receive different colors under the coloring C . The minimum number of colors required for a gamma coloring of G is called the gamma chromatic number of G and is denoted by $\chi_\gamma(G)$. Our aim is to find the gamma chromatic number of Mycielskian graphs. **Methods:** Here, we obtain gamma coloring for Mycielskian graph $\mu(G)$ from a gamma coloring of G by generalizing the give gamma coloring of G . To prove $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) \leq m$ for a graph G , we gave a gamma coloring to $\mu(G)$ using m colors. To prove $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = m$ for a graph G , we first proved that $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) \geq m$ and then gave a gamma coloring to $\mu(G)$ using m colors. **Finding:** In this paper, we have initiated a study on Gamma coloring for Mycielskian graph $\mu(G)$ of a given graph G . We have proved that, the gamma chromatic number χ_γ for $\mu(G)$ is either $\chi_\gamma(G)$ or $\chi_\gamma(G) + 1$ and thus, we classify the class of all connected graphs into two classes namely Class-1 and Class-2 graphs. Graphs G for which $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G)$ are of Class-1 and rest of the graphs are of Class-2. Conditions under which a graph G becomes Class-1/ Class-2 have been established. **Novelty:** One can investigate towards finding a structural characterization of graph G with $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G)$ or $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G) + 1$. Gamma coloring is a new variation of graph coloring in which the concepts of coloring and domination are linked using the condition that the coloring admits a dominating set in which every vertex receives different colors and, in this paper, we study about the gamma coloring of Mycielskian graph $\mu(G)$ of a graph G .

Keywords: Coloring; Dominating Set; Colorful Set; Mycielskian Graphs; Gamma Coloring

1 Introduction

All graphs considered in this paper are connected, simple, finite and undirected graphs. A coloring of a graph G is a function from $V(G)$ to a set of colors which assigns different colors to adjacent vertices. The minimum number of colors needed for a proper coloring of G is called the chromatic number of G and is denoted by $\chi(G)$. A proper coloring of G using $\chi(G)$ colors is called a χ -coloring of G . A subset U of $V(G)$ is said to be a

dominating set of G if every vertex of $V(G)$ is either in U or has a neighbor in U . The minimum cardinality of a dominating set of G is called the domination number of G and is denoted by $\gamma(G)$. A γ -set is a dominating set with cardinality $\gamma(G)$.

A subset U of $V(G)$ is said to be a total dominating set of G if every vertex of $V(G)$ has an adjacent vertex in U . The minimum cardinality of a total dominating set of G is called the total domination number of G and is denoted by $\gamma_t(G)$.

Let C be a proper coloring of a graph G . A subset U of $V(G)$ is said to be C -colorful if every vertex of U receives different color under the coloring C . A subset U of $V(G)$ is said to be color transversal with respect to the coloring C if U intersects every color class of the coloring C . The study of a graph theoretical parameter in Mycielskian construction of graphs is one of the interesting research fields in graph theory. Some of such studies are Dominator coloring of Mycielskian graphs⁽¹⁾, strong coloring of Mycielskian graphs⁽²⁾, connectivity of Mycielskian graphs^(3,4), packing coloring of Mycielskian graphs⁽⁵⁾, total chromatic number of Mycielskian graphs⁽⁶⁾, diameter of Mycielskian of graphs⁽⁷⁾, total weight choosability of Mycielskian graphs⁽⁸⁾ and Hamilton-connected Mycielskian graphs^(9,10). In this paper we define the notion of gamma coloring and discuss about gamma coloring of Mycielskian graphs.

2 Gamma Coloring of graphs

In this section, we introduce the notion of gamma coloring of a graph along with an example.

Definition 2.1: A proper coloring C of a graph G is said to be a gamma coloring of G if there exists a dominating set which is C -colorful. The gamma chromatic number $\chi_\gamma(G)$ is the minimum number of colors needed for a gamma coloring. A gamma coloring that uses $\chi_\gamma(G)$ colors is called a minimum gamma coloring (or) a χ_γ -coloring of G .

Remark 2.2: Certainly, for any graph G , the trivial coloring (that assigns distinct colors to distinct vertices) serves as a gamma coloring of G to which the whole vertex set $V(G)$ is a colorful dominating set. Therefore, every graph admits a gamma coloring and so the parameter $\chi_\gamma(G)$ is well-defined for all graphs.

Fig 1. A Graph G with

Example 2.3: Consider the graph G shown in Figure 1. It is clear that, $\chi(G) = 2$ and $\gamma(G) = 2$. Therefore, $\chi_\gamma(G) \geq 2$. Further, since $C = ((w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4, w_5, w_6, w_8), (w_7, w_9))$ and $S = (w_7, w_9)$ is the only dominating set of G with cardinality 2 which is not C -colorful, it follows that $\chi_\gamma(G) \neq 2$ and thus $\chi_\gamma(G) \geq 3$. Also, $C = ((w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4, w_5, w_6, w_8), (w_7), \{w_9\})$ is a coloring of G to which (w_7, w_9) is a colorful dominating set so that C is a gamma coloring of G and hence $\chi_\gamma(G) \leq 3$. Thus, $\chi_\gamma(G) = 3$.

Suppose C is a χ_γ -coloring of a graph G with a colorful dominating set D . Then D has at most $\chi_\gamma(G)$ vertices so that $\gamma(G) \leq |D| \leq \chi_\gamma(G)$. It is also certain that $\chi_\gamma(G) \geq \chi(G)$ and thus we have the following observation.

Observation 2.4: For any graph G , we have $\chi_\gamma(G) \geq \max(\gamma(G), \chi(G))$.

3 Gamma Chromatic number of Mycielskian graphs

In this section we discuss about the gamma coloring of Mycielskian graph $\mu(G)$ of a graph G . For the sake of completeness let us recall the definition of Mycielskian graph of a graph G .

Definition 3.1: Let G be a graph with vertex set $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$, edge set E and let $V' = \{v'_1, v'_2, \dots, v'_n\}$. The Mycielskian graph $\mu(G)$ of G , is the graph with vertex set $V(\mu(G)) = V \cup V' \cup \{u\}$ and edge set $E(\mu(G)) = E \cup \{v'_i v_j / v_i v_j \in E\} \cup \{u v'_i / v'_i \in V'\}$. The vertex v'_i is called the twin vertex of v_i and u is called the root vertex of $\mu(G)$. The Mycielskian graph of P_4 is given in Figure 2.

Fig 2. Mycielskian graph of P4

It has been proved in⁽¹¹⁾ that, the chromatic number of $\mu(G)$ is always $\chi(G) + 1$ and in⁽¹²⁾ that, the domination number of $\mu(G)$ is $\gamma(G) + 1$. However, in the case of gamma coloring, we have the following result.

Theorem 3.2: For any graph G, $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G)$ or $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G) + 1$.

Proof: Consider a gamma coloring f_1 of G using $\chi_\gamma(G)$ colors with a colorful dominating set D_1 . Let us give a gamma coloring g_1 to $\mu(G)$ using $\chi_\gamma(G) + 1$ colors as follows. Define $g_1(v_i) = g_1(v'_i) = f_1(v_i)$ and assign a new color to the root vertex u . We first prove that g_1 is a proper coloring of $\mu(G)$. Let $e \in E(\mu(G))$. Then $e = v_i v_j$ or $e = v'_i v'_j$ or $e = u v'_i$. If $e = v_i v_j$ or $e = v'_i v'_j$, then $v_i v_j \in E(G)$ which implies that $f_1(v_i) \neq f_1(v_j)$ and hence $g_1(v_i) \neq g_1(v_j)$. If $e = u v'_i$, then $g_1(v_i) \neq g_1(u)$ as $g_1(u)$ is a new color. Thus g_1 is a proper coloring. Certainly, $D_1 \cup \{u\}$ is a dominating set of $\mu(G)$ as D_1 is a dominating set of G. Since $g_1(v_i) = f_1(v_i)$ for all $v_i \in V$ and D_1 is a f_1 -colorful set in G, it follows that $D_1 \cup \{u\}$ is a g_1 -colorful set in $\mu(G)$. Thus $D_1 \cup \{u\}$ is a colorful dominating set of $\mu(G)$ and therefore $\mu(G)$ has a gamma coloring using $\chi_\gamma(G) + 1$ colors and hence $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) \leq \chi_\gamma(G) + 1$.

Let us now prove that, $\chi_\gamma(G) \leq \chi_\gamma(\mu(G))$. Consider a minimum gamma coloring g_2 of $\mu(G)$ using $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G))$ colors with a colorful dominating set S. We obtain a gamma coloring f_2 to G using $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G))$ colors as follows. Define $f_2(v_i) = g_2(v'_i)$ if $v'_i \in S$ and $f_2(v_i) = g_2(v_i)$ otherwise. Let us first show that f_2 is a proper coloring of G. Let $v_i v_j \in E(G)$. Then, $v_i v_j, v'_i v'_j, v_i v'_j \in E(\mu(G))$. If $v'_i, v'_j \notin S$, then $g_2(v_i) \neq g_2(v_j)$ as $v_i v_j \in E(\mu(G))$ and hence $f_2(v_i) \neq f_2(v_j)$. If $v'_i \in S$ and $v'_j \notin S$, then $g_2(v'_i) \neq g_2(v_j)$ as $v'_i v_j \in E(\mu(G))$ and hence $f_2(v_i) \neq f_2(v_j)$. If $v'_i \notin S$ and $v'_j \in S$, then $g_2(v_i) \neq g_2(v'_j)$ as $v'_i v'_j \in E(\mu(G))$ and hence $f_2(v_i) \neq f_2(v_j)$. If $v'_i, v'_j \in S$, then as S is colorful, $g_2(v'_i) \neq g_2(v'_j)$ and hence $f_2(v_i) \neq f_2(v_j)$. Thus, whenever we have $v_i v_j \in E(G)$, we have $f_2(v_i) \neq f_2(v_j)$ and hence f_2 is a proper coloring of G.

Let $D_2 = \{v_i \in V(G) / v_i \in S \text{ or } v'_i \in S\}$. Let us claim that D_2 is a colorful dominating set in G. We first verify that D_2 is a dominating set of G. Let $v_j \in V - D_2$. Then, $v_j \notin S$. Since S is a dominating set in $\mu(G)$, either there exists a vertex $v_i \in S$ such that $v_i v_j \in E(\mu(G))$ or there exists a vertex $v'_i \in S$ such that $v'_i v_j \in E(\mu(G))$. In either case, we have, $v_i \in D_2$ and $v_i v_j \in E(G)$. Therefore, D_2 is a dominating set in G. Let $v_i, v_j \in D_2$. Then $v'_i, v'_j \in S$ or $v'_i \in S, v'_j \notin S$ or $v'_i \notin S, v'_j \in S$ or $v'_i, v'_j \notin S$. If $v'_i, v'_j \in S$, then $g_2(v'_i) \neq g_2(v'_j)$ as S is colorful in $\mu(G)$ and hence $f_2(v_i) \neq f_2(v_j)$. If $v'_i \in S$ and $v'_j \notin S$, then $v'_i v_j \in E(\mu(G))$ and as S is colorful in $\mu(G)$, $g_2(v'_i) \neq g_2(v_j)$ and hence $f_2(v_i) \neq f_2(v_j)$. If $v'_i \notin S$ and $v'_j \in S$, then $v_i v'_j \in E(\mu(G))$ and as S is colorful in $\mu(G)$, $g_2(v_i) \neq g_2(v'_j)$ and hence $f_2(v_i) \neq f_2(v_j)$. If $v'_i, v'_j \notin S$, then $v_i v_j \in E(\mu(G))$ and as S is colorful in $\mu(G)$, $g_2(v_i) \neq g_2(v_j)$ and hence $f_2(v_i) \neq f_2(v_j)$. Thus D_2 is a colorful dominating set and therefore G has a gamma coloring using $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G))$ colors and hence $\chi_\gamma(G) \leq \chi_\gamma(\mu(G))$ which implies that $\chi_\gamma(G) \leq \chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) \leq \chi_\gamma(G) + 1$. Thus $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G))$ is either $\chi_\gamma(G)$ or $\chi_\gamma(G) + 1$. ■

In view of Theorem 3.2, the set of all connected graphs can be classified into two groups namely Class-1 graphs and Class-2 graphs. Class-1 graphs consist of all connected graphs G with $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G)$ whereas Class-2 graphs consist of all connected graphs G with $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G) + 1$. The following proposition shows that each of these classes contains infinitely

many members.

Proposition 3.3 : Let $k \geq 3$ be an integer. Then

- (i) There exists a graph G such that $\chi_\gamma(G) = k$ and $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = k$.
- (ii) There exists a graph H such that $\chi_\gamma(H) = k$ and $\chi_\gamma(\mu(H)) = k + 1$.

Proof: For the given $k \geq 3$, we construct a required graph G as follows.

Consider a star graph on k vertices with v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{k-1} as pendent vertices and w as the center vertex. Now, attach exactly two pendent vertices at each of v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{k-1} and label them as shown in Figure 3. Let us first show that $\chi_\gamma(G) = k$.

Fig 3. A graph G with

Clearly $(\{v_1\}, \{v_2\}, \dots, \{v_{k-1}\}, \{w, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{2k-2}\}) \setminus \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{k-1}\}$ is a colorful dominating set D . $|D| \geq \gamma(G) = k - 1$. $|D| \geq k$,

If $|D| = k - 1$, then $D = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{k-1}\}$. Since w is a neighbor to all the vertices in D which is colorful, we need a new color for w and hence at least k colors are required for a gamma coloring of G and therefore, $\chi_\gamma(G) \geq k$. Thus, $\chi_\gamma(G) = k$.

Now, we prove that $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = k$. By Theorem 3.2, $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) \geq \chi_\gamma(G)$ and hence $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) \geq k$. Let us obtain a gamma coloring of $\mu(G)$ with k colors. Consider the coloring $(\{v_1, u_1\}, \{v_2, v'_1, v'_2\}, \{v_3, v'_3\}, \dots, \{v_{k-1}, v'_{k-1}\}, \{w, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{2k-2}, w', u'_1, u'_2, \dots\})$. Clearly, it is a gamma coloring of $\mu(G)$ using k colors in which $\{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{k-1}, w'\}$ is a colorful dominating set and therefore, $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) \leq k$. Thus, $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = k = \chi_\gamma(G)$.

Complete graphs on k vertices serve the purpose as proved in Theorem 3.7.

The following theorem provides a necessary and sufficient condition for a graph G in terms of $\mu(G)$ to be of Class-2 graph.

Theorem 3.4 : $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G) + 1$ if and only if there is a χ_γ -coloring of $\mu(G)$ admitting a colorful dominating set containing the root vertex u .

Proof: Suppose there is a χ_γ -coloring f of $\mu(G)$ admitting a colorful dominating set D containing u . Let $c = f(u)$. Now, let us give a gamma coloring g to G using $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) - 1$ colors as follows. Define $h(v_i) = f(v'_i)$ if $v'_i \in D$ and define $h(v_i) = f(v_i)$ otherwise. Also, define $S = \{v_i \in V(G) / v_i \in D \text{ or } v'_i \in D\}$. Then by the second part in the proof of Theorem 3.2, h is a gamma coloring of G with S as a colorful dominating set. Note that the color c is not used by any of the vertex in S for if $v'_i \in D$, then $h(v_i) = f(v'_i) \neq f(u) = c$ and if $v'_i \notin D$ and $v_i \in D$, then $u, v_i \in D$. Since D is f -colorful, we have $h(v_i) = f(v_i) \neq f(u) = c$.

Suppose that $h(v_i) = c$ for some i . Then, $v_i, v'_i \notin D$. Now, recolor the vertex v_i such that $h(v_i) = f(v'_i) \neq c$. The coloring h is still a proper coloring of G because of $N(v'_i) \cap V(G) = N(v_i) \cap V(G)$. Repeat the above process of recoloring until $h(v_i) \neq c$ for all i . Thus, we have a proper coloring h of G using $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) - 1$ colors in which S is a colorful dominating set. Hence $\chi_\gamma(G) \leq \chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) - 1$ which implies that $\chi_\gamma(G) + 1 \leq \chi_\gamma(\mu(G))$ and by Theorem 3.2, $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G) + 1$.

Conversely, let us assume that $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G) + 1$. Consider a gamma coloring f of G using $\chi_\gamma(G)$ colors with a colorful dominating set D . By similar argument as in the first part of Theorem 3.2, we can give a gamma coloring h to $\mu(G)$ with $\chi_\gamma(G) + 1$ colors in which u is in a colorful dominating set which completes the proof.

Theorem 3.4 is helpful in proving certain families of graph are of Class-2. For example, paths, cycles and complete graphs are of Class-2 as shown below.

Theorem 3.5: Path graphs are of Class-2.

Proof: Let $P_n = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$. It is clear that $\gamma(P_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil$. Also, it has been proved in⁽⁵⁾ that for a graph G , $\gamma(\mu(G)) = \gamma(G) + 1$ and therefore $\gamma(\mu(P_n)) = \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil + 1$. Hence by Observation 2.4, $\chi_\gamma(\mu(P_n)) \geq \gamma(\mu(P_n)) = \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil + 1$. So, in view of Theorem 3.4, it is enough to obtain a gamma coloring C of $\mu(P_n)$ using $\lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil + 1$ colors with the property that there is a C -

colorful dominating set of $\mu(P_n)$ containing the root vertex u . We do it in the following cases. Let v'_i be the twin vertex of v_i in $\mu(P_n)$ and u be the root vertex of $\mu(P_n)$.

Case 1: $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

In this case, $n = 3k$ for some natural number k and $\lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil + 1 = k + 1$. Let us give a gamma coloring C to $\mu(P_n)$ using $k + 1$ colors as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} V_1 &= (v_2, v'_2, v_4, v'_4) \cup (v_{3j}, v'_{3j} : 2 \leq j \leq k), \\ V_2 &= (v_1, v'_1, v_3, v'_3, v_5, v'_5) \cup (v_{3j-2}, v'_{3j-2} : 3 \leq j \leq k), \\ V_i &= (v_{3i-1}, v'_{3i-1}) \text{ for all } 3 \leq i \leq k \text{ and } V_{k+1} = (u). \end{aligned}$$

Clearly $C = (V_1, V_2, \dots, V_{k+1})$ is a proper coloring of $\mu(P_n)$. The coloring of $\mu(P_6)$ is illustrated in Figure 4. Moreover, as $D = (v_2, v_5, \dots, v_{3k-1})$ is a dominating set of P_n , $S = D \cup \{u\}$ is a dominating set of $\mu(P_n)$. Also, $S \cap V_i = (v_{3i-1})$ for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ and $S \cap V_{k+1} = (u)$. Thus S is C -colorful dominating set of $\mu(P_n)$ which implies that $\chi_\gamma(\mu(P_n)) \leq k + 1$ and hence $\chi_\gamma(\mu(P_n)) = k + 1$. Thus C is a χ_γ -coloring of $\mu(P_n)$ with a colorful dominating set S containing u as desired.

Fig 4. Gamma coloring of with 3 colors

Case 2: $n \equiv 1$ or $2 \pmod{3}$.

In this case $n = 3k - 1$ or $n = 3k - 2$ for some natural number k and $\lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil + 1 = k + 1$. Let us give a gamma coloring C to $\mu(P_n)$ using $k + 1$ colors as follows. Let

$$V_1 = \begin{cases} (v_2, v'_2, v_4, v'_4) \cup (v_{3j-3}, v'_{3j-3} : 3 \leq j \leq k) \cup (v_{3k-1}, v'_{3k-1}) & \text{if } n = 3k - 1 \text{ or } n = 3k - 2 \\ (v_2, v'_2, v_4, v'_4) \cup (v_{3j-3}, v'_{3j-3} : 3 \leq j \leq k) & \text{if } n = 3k - 1 \end{cases}$$

$$V_2 = (v_1, v'_1, v_3, v'_3, v_5, v'_5) \cup (v_{3j-2}, v'_{3j-2} : 3 \leq j \leq k - 1),$$

$$V_i = (v_{3i-1}, v'_{3i-1}) \text{ for all } 3 \leq i \leq k - 1,$$

$$V_k = (v_{3k-2}, v'_{3k-2})$$

and $V_{k+1} = (u)$.

Then $C = (V_1, V_2, \dots, V_{k+1})$ is a proper coloring of $\mu(P_n)$. Moreover, as $D = (v_2, v_5, \dots, v_{3k-4}, v_{3k-2})$ is a dominating set of P_n , $S = D \cup \{u\}$ is a dominating set of $\mu(P_n)$. Also, $S \cap V_i = (v_{3i-1})$ for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k - 1\}$, $S \cap V_k = (v_{3i-2})$ and $S \cap V_{k+1} = (u)$. Thus, S is C -colorful dominating set of $\mu(P_n)$ which implies that $\chi_\gamma(\mu(P_n)) \leq k + 1$ and hence $\chi_\gamma(\mu(P_n)) = k + 1$. Thus C is a χ_γ -coloring of $\mu(P_n)$ with a colorful dominating set S containing u as desired.

By a similar argument we can prove the following theorem for cycle graphs.

Theorem 3.6: Cycle graphs are of Class-2.

Theorem 3.7: Complete graphs are of Class-2.

Proof: Let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the vertices of K_n . It is clear that $\chi(K_n) = n$. Also, it has been proved in⁽¹²⁾ that for a graph G , $\chi(\mu(G)) = \chi(G) + 1$ and therefore $\chi(\mu(K_n)) = n + 1$. Hence by Observation 2.4, $\chi_\gamma(\mu(K_n)) \geq \chi(\mu(K_n)) = n + 1$. In view of Theorem 3.4, it is enough to obtain a gamma coloring for $\mu(K_n)$ using $n + 1$ colors admitting a colorful dominating set

containing the root vertex u . Let v'_i be the twin vertex of v_i in $\mu(K_n)$. Let $V_i = (v_i, v'_i)$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k$, and $V_{k+1} = (u)$. As v_i and v'_i are not adjacent in $\mu(K_n)$, it is clear that $C = (V_1, V_2, \dots, V_{k+1})$ is a proper coloring of $\mu(K_n)$. Also, $S = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n, u\}$ is a dominating set of $\mu(K_n)$. Clearly, $S \cap V_i = \{v_i\}$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k$ and $S \cap V_{k+1} = \{u\}$ so that S is a colorful dominating set of $\mu(K_n)$. Hence C is a gamma coloring of $\mu(K_n)$ with $n + 1$ colors which implies that $\chi_\gamma(\mu(K_n)) \leq n + 1$ and thus $\chi_\gamma(\mu(K_n)) = n + 1$. Therefore, C is a χ_γ -coloring of $\mu(K_n)$ admitting a colorful dominating set S containing u . Thus, by Theorem 3.4, it follows that, complete graphs are of Class-2.

Theorem 3.4 provides a condition for a graph G to be of Class-2 graph in terms of minimum gamma coloring of $\mu(G)$. In the following theorem, we obtain a sufficient condition for a graph G to be of Class-1 graph in terms of minimum gamma coloring G .

Theorem 3.8 : If a graph G has a $\chi_\gamma(G)$ -coloring $(V_1, V_2, \dots, V_{\chi_\gamma(G)})$ with the following properties.

- (i) There exists a positive integer m such that $N[v]$ is not a color transversal for every vertex $v \in V_m$.
- (ii) There exists a colorful total dominating set D such that $D \cap V_p = \emptyset$ for some $p \neq m$.

Then $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G)$.

Proof: Let G has a $\chi_\gamma(G)$ -coloring $(V_1, V_2, \dots, V_{\chi_\gamma(G)})$ with the given properties and let f be the corresponding coloring function. For each $v_i \in V_m$, being $N[v_i]$ is not a color transversal, there exists j such that $N(v_i) \cap V_j = \emptyset$ and let c_{v_i} be the color used to color the vertices of V_j . Let k be the color used to color the vertices of V_m . Let us give a gamma coloring h to $\mu(G)$ using $\chi_\gamma(G)$ colors as follows. Define $h(v_i) = f(v_i)$ for all $v_i \in V$, $h(v'_i) = f(v_i)$ if $v_i \notin V_m$ and define $h(v'_i) = c_{v_i}$ if $v_i \in V_m$ and $h(u) = k$. Let us first prove that, h is a proper coloring of $\mu(G)$. Let $e \in \mu(G)$. Then $e = v_i v_j$ or $e = v'_i v_j$ or $e = uv'_i$. If $e = v_i v_j$, then $v_i v_j \in E(G)$ which implies that $f(v_i) \neq f(v_j)$ and hence $h(v_i) \neq h(v_j)$. If $e = v'_i v_j$, then $v_i v_j \in E(G)$ which implies that $f(v_i) \neq f(v_j)$. If $v_i \notin V_m$, then $h(v'_i) = f(v_i) \neq f(v_j) = h(v_j)$. If $v_i \in V_m$, then by the selection of c_{v_i} , the color c_{v_i} is not used by adjacent vertices of v_i and therefore $f(v_j) \neq c_{v_i}$. Thus, we have $h(v'_i) = c_{v_i} \neq f(v_j) = h(v_j)$. Clearly, from the definition of h , $h(v'_i) \neq k$ for all $v'_i \in V'$. If $e = uv'_i$ then $h(u) = k \neq h(v'_i)$ and hence h is a proper coloring.

Let $u_d \in V_p$ and $D' = D \cup \{u'_d\}$. Since D is a total dominating set, for every $v_i \in V$ there exists $v_j \in D$ such that v_i is adjacent to v_j and therefore v'_i is adjacent to v_j which implies that D dominates V and V' . Also, u is dominated by u'_d . Hence D' is a dominating set of $\mu(G)$. Since $h(v_i) = f(v_i)$ for all $v_i \in V$ and D is f -colorful in G , we have D is h -colorful in $\mu(G)$. Also, in $\mu(G)$, u'_d receives the color used by the color class V_p and $D \cap V_p = \emptyset$ which implies that D' is colorful. Thus $\mu(G)$ admits a coloring using $\chi_\gamma(G)$ colors in which a dominating set D' is colorful. Hence $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) \leq \chi_\gamma(G)$ and by Theorem 3.2, $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G)$.

Remark 3.9: The converse of Theorem 3.8 is not true. For example, consider the graph G shown in Figure 5 which is the graph constructed as in Proposition 3.3 (i) with $k=3$. From the construction of the graph, it is clear that $\chi_\gamma(G) = 3 = \chi_\gamma(\mu(G))$. Consider a χ_γ -coloring $C = \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}$ of G . Let D be a C -colorful total dominating set. Clearly, $|D| \leq \chi_\gamma(G) = 3$ But $\{v_1, v_2, w\}$ is the only total dominating set with at most three elements. Hence $D = \{v_1, v_2, w\}$ is the only C -colorful total dominating set. Since D uses all the three colors of C , there does not exist a color class V_p with $D \cap V_p = \emptyset$

Fig 5. A counter example to the converse of Theorem 3.8

4 Conclusion

We have initiated a study on Gamma coloring for Mycielskian graph $\mu(G)$ of a given graph G . We have proved that the gamma chromatic number χ_γ for $\mu(G)$ is either $\chi_\gamma(G)$ or $\chi_\gamma(G) + 1$ and thus the class of all connected graphs is classified into two classes namely Class-1 and Class-2 graphs. Graphs G for which $\chi_\gamma(\mu(G)) = \chi_\gamma(G)$ are of Class-1 and the rest of graphs are of Class-2. Conditions under which a graph G becomes Class-1/ Class-2 have been established by which some families of Class-1 / Class-2 graphs have been characterized. There are still scopes for further research on this topic. For instance, the following are some interesting problems.

(1) Theorem 3.4 provides a necessary and sufficient condition under which a graph falls in Class-2; however, it does not infer about the structure of those graphs. So, it is worthy finding a structural characterization of Class-1/ Class-2 graphs.

(2) Characterize trees which are of Class-1/ Class-2.

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